

STRUCTURAL RESPONSE AND PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODELLING OF OUT-OF-PLANE JOINTS WITH A VISCO-ELASTIC OR STANDARD INSERT MATERIAL

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this paper is to investigate the static structural response of two types of out-of-plane joint: a Tee-joint and a top hat stiffener. In each case a new geometry with a visco-elastic insert is examined and the effect of these change in parameters on the response of the joints¹ under a particular load type. Furthermore, a progressive damage methodology is applied to the joints in question to reach a better understanding of the initiation and progression of failure and ultimate failure load. The stress distributions at particular load steps lead to predictive values for the initiation of failure. The progressive damage model successfully identifies the loads at which failure initiates and the mode of failure. The model propagates failure throughout the joint until no further load can be sustained.

KEYWORDS: out-of-plane joints, Tee joints, top hat stiffeners, progressive damage modelling, plane stress, visco-elastic

INTRODUCTION

Large fibre-reinforced plastic (FRP) structures, by necessity of design and production constraints, have a number of in-plane and out-of-plane joints in their topologies. In-plane joints have been the subject of attention of many researchers, for example, Godwin and Matthews [6] and Matthews *et. al.* [9], with attention being focused on analytical treatments, numerical analyses, experimental studies, failure criteria and material aspects.

Arguably, the more difficult problem is the one that pertains to load transfer between two orthogonally placed members meeting at a joint. Two such out-of-plane joints, a Tee-joint and a top-hat stiffener are illustrated in figure 1a,b and figure 2a,b. There is now a growing body of literature on the behaviour of these out-of-plane joints. Recent theoretical models, incorporating layered (finite) elements and a variety of failure criteria, has successfully characterised through numerical analyses both single skin [13] and sandwich [15],[17] joints under representative static loading. This work has been supplemented by experimental programmes studying failure mechanisms [7] and stress patterns [4]. The work has been extended to studying the long-term effects of such joints under repetitive, cyclic loading[14] including inception and progression of failure as well as approaches to life modelling. All

¹ Joints, in the context of this paper, will encompass, where obvious, stiffeners.

such work has formed the basis of writing a procedure for the synthesis of design variables for typical single skin tee joints in ship and civil construction [3].

What is now being envisaged is to better utilise the joint in a dynamic response mode. One way to achieve this is to investigate the influence of high strain-to-failure, viscoelastic materials. It has been shown that the use of such materials could lead to better energy absorption capabilities in structures. Preliminary work, ref. 8., has demonstrated that a tapered viscoelastic layer placed between a GRP beam and a steel supporting substrate can produce a significant absorption of vibrational energy. One of the aims of this paper is to consider the placement of such material in a typical ship structural tee-joint or top hat stiffener on the strength and stiffness characteristics.

DETAILS OF THE SPECIMENS

Tee-Joints

Tee joints are constructed at the intersection of two orthogonal plates, the web (e.g., a bulkhead) and the flange (e.g., the hull shell), see figure 1a,b. The plates are connected by means of a curved overlaminates on both sides of the 'upright' or web. The void formed between the overlaminates and the web and flange is filled with a resinous insert material which has to be compatible with the cloth material and have a high yield strength.

The main function of the Tee connection is to transfer flexural, tensile and/or shear loads between the web and the flange. For example, a flooded hold would cause a Tee-joint with hydrostatic pressure on one side to experience bending moments and shear loads, whilst an impact load on the hull from example docking or grounding, will cause a rotation of the flange about the joint base.

Two types of Tee-joints are investigated:

- Tee-joint with a standard fillet resin insert of crestomer 1152PA
- Tee-joint with a flexible visco-elastic fillet resin insert

Refer to Ref.1 for a full description of material properties and joint geometry.

Figure 1a: Standard Tee Joint

Figure 1b: Flexible Tee Joint

Top-Hat Stiffener

Top-hat stiffeners are the most common form of stiffening large unsupported spans of FRP plated panels. Like the Tee-joint, this stiffener comprises of two orthogonally placed plate structures, the frame and the shell or flange, see figure 2a,b. Its role is to transmit shear stresses between the shell and frame flanges under local bending caused by lateral pressure or concentrated lateral loads. The frame, which is formed around a core material such as foam or balsa, is connected to the shell or flange by a curved overlaminates on either side. The void formed between the overlaminates, the frame and core, and the flange, is filled with the resinous insert material.

Two types of Top-hat stiffeners are investigated:

- Top-hat with a standard insert of crestone 1152PA
- Top-hat with a flexible visco-elastic insert

Material and geometric properties are referenced in ref. 1.

Figure 2a: Standard Top Hat Stiffener

Figure 2b: Flexible Top Hat Stiffener

MODELLING CONSIDERATIONS

No experimental data exist for the actual laid-up standard or flexible joints. The numerical models are difficult to validate without these results. However, a large number of numerical models have been generated, either in two- or three dimensions, with different mesh densities, material properties, element type and so forth [1]. This represents an attempt to develop a trend in structural behaviour. Ultimately providing a series of models that can be used with confidence on the basis that errors inherent with one model will be unlikely to exist in all the other models. One consequence of this approach demonstrates the applicability of using plane strain or plane stress as an approximation to a full 3D solution. This reduces computational effort dramatically.

The models were created using ANSYS 5.4 and ABAQUS 5.7. The models were meshed with four node quadrilateral plane stress elements (ANSYS PLANE42, or ABAQUS CPS4) with a thickness option. Each ply was modelled as one element thick and material directions defined according to ply orientation.

LOADS, MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Loading

Phillips [11], Hawkins and Sheno [13] and Sheno *et al.* [14], amongst others, characterise various in-service load scenarios associated with Tee-joints and top hat stiffeners. For both types of joint, the primary problem has been in joint debonding and not in web or stiffener frame buckling. The application of tensile loading is therefore required.

For the Tee-joint, the load is applied underneath, along the centreline of the flange, with clamps either side of the web on the upper surface of the flange, effectively a three-point bend. This type of loading is experienced when docking, berthing or grounding and also with the implosion of shock bubbles on the intermediate shell plating.

The top hat is loaded with a tensile load applied to the flange of the stiffener. It represents a load state typically associated with a tank under test or when a shock bubble implodes resulting in a negative pressure on the shell plating [14]. It also produces premature delaminations in the overlaminates associated with this type of loading.

Boundary Conditions

To represent these three-point load cases in the numerical model, degree of freedom constraints are required either side of the web or frame and a force applied on the underneath of the flange at the centreline. The constraints are placed 500mm apart (the laid-up specimens are 1000mm in width), either side of the centreline. Both nodes are prevented from translation in the y-direction but to restrict a rigid body motion, one of the nodes is restricted in the x-direction also. Coordinate directions are given in figures 1 and 2.

Material Properties

Linear material properties have been used throughout for the overlaminates, web, frame, core, flange and also the insert materials.

PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODEL

Progressive damage modelling first determines the load and location at which a material in the joint first fails. From that point onwards, the failure at that point is included in subsequent analyses. The progression of damage is therefore determinable and so too the ultimate collapse load.

Progressive failure analysis is based on the assumption that the damaged material can be substituted with an equivalent material with degraded properties. This can be accomplished by using a limited discount, or stiffness reduction, method used successfully, among others, by Padhi *et al* [10] on composite plates and Camanho and Matthews [18] on CFRP bolted joints.

The method for stiffness reduction is simple but effective. For the mode of failure associated with matrix cracking at a material integration point, the transverse modulus E_y , and Poisson's ratio ν_{yx} , are reduced to zero. However, the longitudinal modulus E_x and the shear modulus G_{xy} remain unchanged. When the failure mode of fibre-matrix shearing is predicted at a material point, the transverse shear modulus G_{xy} and Poisson's ratio ν_{yx} are reduced to zero.

However the longitudinal modulus E_x and transverse modulus E_y remain unchanged. If the failure mode associated with fibre failure is detected, then the material is deemed to have lost complete stiffness at the integration point.

Failure Criteria

In general, failure criteria for composite materials can be expressed in terms of a single tensor polynomial failure criterion such as that proposed by Tsai. Failure is assumed to occur if the following condition is satisfied:

$$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j + F_{ijk} \sigma_i \sigma_j \sigma_k + \dots \geq 1$$

The two dimensional form of the above polynomial is expressed as:

$$F_1 \sigma_1 + F_2 \sigma_2 + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + F_{11} \sigma_1^2 + F_{22} \sigma_2^2 + F_{66} \sigma_6^2 \geq 1$$

In the expressions, the notations, σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_6 ($\sigma_6 = \sigma_{12}$) are the in-plane stresses in the material coordinate directions, and F_{ijk} are the failure indices, determined from material strength parameters. The failure modes associated with matrix cracking, fibre breakage or fibre/matrix shear are predicted using the Tsai-Hill criterion [10].

Tsai-Hill Criterion

The failure indices for the Tsai-Hill criterion are

$$F_1 = 0, F_2 = 0, F_{12} = -\frac{1}{2X^2}, F_{11} = \frac{1}{X^2}, F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y^2}, F_{66} = \frac{1}{S_C^2}$$

where if

$\sigma_1 > 0$, $X = X_T$; otherwise, $X = X_C$.

and if

$\sigma_2 > 0$, $Y = Y_T$; otherwise, $Y = Y_C$

X_T , X_C , Y_T , Y_C and S_C are strength parameters (UTS and UCS in the X, Y and XY directions).

For the interactive polynomial criterion, if failure occurs the following expressions are used to determine the failure mode:

$$H_1 = F_1 \sigma_1 + F_{11} \sigma_1^2$$

$$H_2 = F_2 \sigma_2 + F_{22} \sigma_2^2$$

$$H_6 = F_{66} \sigma_6^2$$

The largest H_i term is selected as the dominant failure mode and the corresponding modulus is reduced to zero. Thus, H_1 corresponds to fibre failure, H_2 corresponds to matrix cracking and H_6 corresponds to fibre-matrix shearing failure.

Analysis Procedure

A typical procedure for progressive failure analysis is given below.

To account for the change in geometry upon loading the load is applied in steps:

1. At the load step, a geometric non-linear analysis is performed until a converged solution is obtained,
2. the stresses at every integration point are evaluated,
3. the stresses at each of those material integration points are then compared with material limits,

4. the contribution of each stress component towards the failure index (H_i) is computed and the stress component which contributes the maximum is identified,
 5. depending on the largest H_i term, the failure mode is determined and the corresponding material properties are degraded accordingly,
 6. the next load step is applied.
- The whole process, 1 to 6, is then repeated.

At some point in the analysis, a dramatic change in the slope of the load-deflection graph indicates an inability of the structure to support additional load. This location is identified as the ultimate failure load.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Tee-joints

Load-Deflection Curves for Tee-Joints with a Standard or Visco-elastic Insert

Figure 3 shows linear load-deflection curves for a Tee-joint with a standard crestomer 1152PA insert compared with the new joint geometry and new visco-elastic insert material. The new geometry joint with a visco-elastic insert is about twice as flexible as the standard joint. It is important to realise that the presence of the visco-elastic resin on the joint stiffness may not be the sole reason for the changed static response of the joint, but that the joint geometry is also a governing factor. In fact, replacing the visco-elastic fillet resin in the new joint with the standard crestomer material actually increases the joint’s stiffness [1]. This shows the overall importance of the visco-elastic resin in changing and improving the flexibility of the joint and describes the new joint geometry as having sandwich type behaviour.

Figure 3: Load-Deflection Plot for Standard and Flexible Tee-Joints.

Structural Response of Standard Crestomer Insert Tee-Joint

The following stress distribution plots are for an applied load of 15kN. At this load the deflection is 2.05mm. Figures 4-6 show the principal stresses in the fillet material, the in-plane stress in the overlamine and the through-thickness stress in the overlamine for the standard insert material joint.

Figure 4: Fillet Principal Stress

Figure 4 shows the principal stress in the fillet material reaches a maximum of around 8.6MPa, the actual UTS for crestomer 1152PA is about 26MPa so it would seem unlikely at this load for the resin to start failing.

Figure 5: In-Plane Stress

Figure 6: Through-Thickness Stress

The in-plane stress distribution along the overlaminates shows a maximum of 30.4MPa whereas the UTS for the overlaminates material is about 206MPa. Again, one can deduce that at this load, no failure will initiate in the in-plane direction of the overlaminates. However, looking at the stress distribution in the through-thickness of the curved overlaminates, figure 6, it is possible to see that the maximum stress is about 11MPa which is just under twice the interlaminar tensile strength (ILTS) limit for the overlaminates. At a load of about 7.5kN, delamination in the outside radius of the curved overlaminates can be predicted.

Structural Response of Visco-Elastic Insert Tee-Joint

The linear load-deflection details of the standard joint predict delamination failure at around 7.5kN with a corresponding deflection of 1.03mm. For the new joint with a visco-elastic insert, an applied load of 5kN already causes a deflection over 1.5mm. The stress distributions are analysed at this load.

Figure 7: Fillet Principal Stress

The principal stress distribution in the fillet is given in figure 7. The maximum stress occurs next to the curved overlaminates, but its value is less than 0.1MPa, much less than the UTS of 26MPa.

Figure 8: In-Plane Stress

Figure 9: Through-Thickness Stress

Figure 8 shows that maximum in-plane stress occurs on the outside of the curved overlaminates and is clearly in tension from the three-point bend. At this load, the maximum

stress reaches a value of 19.7MPa, which is well below the maximum permissible stress of 206MPa.

Figure 9 represents the stress distribution in the through-thickness direction. The maximum stress occurs at a region where the base of the web, the inside of the overlamine and the top corner of the fillet resin connect. This area is likely to be highly stressed, especially with a low stiffness fillet resin that is less able to distribute the load across the joint. Comparing the maximum stress locations and values in this region and in the adjacent region in the fillet resin reflects the inability of the fillet resin to distribute stress.

The limit of 7MPa for ILTS has been exceeded in the overlamine radius, suggesting initial delamination in this area. There is another region of high through-thickness stress which is present on the outside of the curved overlamine. These stress values are between 6 and 15MPa which is enough for delamination.

Progressive Damage Model

From the numerical models, the standard insert joint seems to be approaching initial failure around 7.5kN and the joint with the flexible insert at around 5kN. The predicted initiation of failure in both cases seems to be in terms of a delamination in the curved overlamine.

Figure 11 shows the load-deflection results from the progressive damage model for a joint with a visco-elastic insert compared with the equivalent linear response. Initiation of failure occurs in the load step predicted by the linear model. At a load of 5kN, the joint stiffness reduces and continues to reduce until ultimate failure.

Figure 21 shows the load increments from 5kN to 45kN in steps of 5kN to produce deflections given in the middle column and areas of failures subsequently found at the end of each load step. At a load of 5kN, delamination has started in the areas near the intersection of the web, overlamine and insert resin and in the top layers of the curved overlamine. This corresponds to those areas highlighted by maximum through-thickness stress distributions, in excess of the ILTS, in the curved overlamine generated by the ANSYS models, figure 9.

The propagation of failure is such that between 5kN and 25kN delamination continues to widen up the web and through the top of the overlamine radius. From 25kN, delamination starts to appear further down the overlamine towards where it meets the flange and along the rest of the overlamine radius. At around, 35kN, fibre failure is evident in the overlamine radius. At this load, the tip of the web has deflected by about 12mm. Little overall element failure seems to occur between 35kN and 40kN despite a further deflection up to 14.5mm at 40kN. However, over 40kN the fibre failure increases dramatically and fibre/matrix shear is evident. At 45kN the deflection is registering about 17.5mm, the amount of material damage is such that the joint is nearing complete failure.

Results for the failure of the standard Tee-joint are not presented here, except in figure 10 as a load-deflection curve. At different load steps, the initiation and propagation can be described as following very much the same failure mechanism.

Figure 10: Damaged and Undamaged Standard Tee Joint

Figure 11: Damaged and Undamaged Flexible Tee Joint

Top-Hat Stiffeners

Load-Deflection Curves for Top-Hat Stiffeners with a Standard or Visco-elastic Insert

Figure 12 shows that the new top-hat stiffener geometry with a visco-elastic insert is over three times as flexible as the standard stiffener with a crestomer 1152PA. As with the Tee-joints, the influence of the change in geometry on the static response is to increase the stiffness over that of the standard stiffener when filled with the same crestomer resin, the large layer of stiff fillet resin under the overlamine contributing to sandwich type behaviour [2].

Figure 12: Load-deflection Plot for Standard and Flexible Top Hat Stiffener

Structural Response of Standard Crestomer Insert Top-Hat Stiffener

The following stress plots are for a three-point bend load of 3kN. At this load the deflection at the centre is about 1.15mm.

Figure 13: Fillet Principal Stress

Figure 13 shows the principal stress in the fillet material. The position of maximum stress occurs in the bottom corner of the fillet resin, adjacent to the root of the curved overlaminates. The maximum value approaches 2.1MPa. The UTS for crestomer 1152PA is about 26MPa so it would seem unlikely at this load for the resin to start failing.

Figure 14: In-Plane Stress

Figure 15: Through Thickness Stress

The in-plane stress distribution along the overlaminates shows a maximum of 12.3MPa in the area under tension. This is of order ten below the ultimate tensile strength for this material. However, looking at the stress distribution in the through-thickness of the curved overlaminates, figure 15, it is possible to see that the maximum stress is 15.3MPa which is twice the expected ILTS limit of 7MPa. Delamination would be anticipated through this area in the outside layers of the curved overlaminates.

Structural Response of Visco-Elastic Insert Top-Hat Stiffener

The standard top-hat stiffener exhibited stress distributions promoting delamination in the overlaminates at a load of 3kN. This corresponds to a deflection of about 1.2mm. At a load of 1kN, the new top-hat stiffener with a visco-elastic insert has already deflected by about 1.4mm. Examining the stress distributions at this load is prudent.

Figure 16: Fillet Principal Stress

The principal stress distribution in the fillet is given in figure 16. The maximum stress occurs where the balsa core, overlaminates radius end and fillet resin meet. The maximum stress is less than 0.2MPa so no failure would be expected in the fillet resin.

Figure 17: In-Plane Stress

Figure 18: Through Thickness Stress

Figure 17 shows that maximum in-plane stress occurs on the outside of the curved overlaminates and is clearly in tension from the three-point bend. At this load, the maximum stress reaches a value of 12.9MPa, which is well below the maximum permissible stress of 206MPa.

Figure 18 represents the stress distribution in the through-thickness direction. The maximum stress occurs on the outside of the curved overlaminates. The stress values are in excess of 7MPa, which is enough for delamination.

Progressive Damage Model

From the numerical models, the standard insert stiffener seems to be approaching initial failure around 1.5kN (twice the ILTS being predicted in the overlaminates at 3kN) and the stiffener with the flexible insert at around 1kN. The initiation of failure in both cases seems to be in terms of a delamination in the curved overlaminates.

Figure 20 shows the load-deflection results from the progressive damage model for a stiffener with a visco-elastic insert compared with the equivalent linear response. The initiation of failure calculated by the progressive damage model occurs in the load step predicted by the linear model. At a load of 1kN, the joint stiffness reduces and continues to reduce until ultimate failure. However, the strength of the joint seems to remain close to the linear result until a load of about 3.5kN.

Figure 21 shows the load increments from 0.5kN to 4.5kN in steps of 0.5kN to produce deflections given in the middle column and areas of failures subsequently found at the end of each load step. It is apparent that at a load of 1kN, delamination has started in those areas highlighted by maximum through-thickness stress distributions in the ANSYS model, figure 18.

The propagation of failure continues throughout the overlaminates and higher up the frame. Although more material failure is apparent the overall strength of the joint remains uncompromised until about 3.5kN. On increasing load, the failure increases with large numbers of fibre breakage and fibre/matrix shear until the joint is incapable of sustaining any further load (greater than 4.5kN).

Very much the same initiation and propagation of failure can be seen with the standard joint although at around twice the load (figure 19) [2].

Figure 19: Damaged and Undamaged Standard Top Hat Stiffener

Figure 20: Damaged and Undamaged Flexible Top Hat Stiffener

Figure 21: Description of failure points with load and deflection for half-overlaminated areas (dashed boxes in figs 1&2)(Left, Tee-joint; Right, top hat stiffener)

CONCLUSIONS

A standard Tee-joint and a top-hat stiffener with a crestomer 1152PA insert and a new joint with a visco-elastic insert have been numerically tested under a three-point bending load. The static structural response of each joint and configuration has been ascertained and insight into the load transfer mechanisms and initiation and subsequent progression of failure provided.

The important differences in the two joints have been identified in ref. 1 and ref. 2. Both joint geometries were very different from their standard designs and the insert materials had vastly different properties. Typically, the volume ratio of insert material to overlaminated is low, which results in the overall response of the structure being dictated by the overlaminated

properties. For the new joints, however, the volume of insert material is so high that the joint exhibits sandwich-type properties. The raised overlamine inherently increases the stiffness of the joint but only if the core material, or insert, is capable of transferring the load as the crestomer 1152PA insert is [1]. When the void is filled with a visco-elastic resin though, the transfer of load is very different and large stresses exist throughout the overlamine, as the visco-elastic resin is not as effective in spreading the applied load. The sandwich stiffness properties are lost through the weak visco-elastic core and the joint flexibility increases.

The progressive damage model picks out the initiation, position and mode of failure. In both the Tee joints and the top hat stiffeners, the initiation of failure is delamination in the curve of the overlamine which propagates outwards and along the overlamine. Finally, with a large amount of delamination, the incidence of fibre breakage and fibre/matrix shear becomes obvious.

The overall difference between the standard joints with a crestomer insert and the new joint geometry with a visco-elastic insert is a dramatic change in flexibility with a corresponding reduction in joint strength for the new geometry and insert. The performance of the new Tee-joint with a visco-elastic core is 1.5 times the flexibility of the standard joint with a crestomer 1152PA insert. For the top hat stiffener, the new geometry, with a visco-elastic insert, produces a joint over three times as flexible as the standard stiffener with a crestomer 1152PA insert. The new Tee-joint under this form of loading appears to reach final failure at about three-quarters of the load of the standard Tee-joint. Likewise, the new top hat stiffener reaches an initiation of failure at about two-thirds the load of the standard stiffener and fails at less than half the load of the standard stiffener.

Despite confidence in the modelling validity by the consistency of numerous numerical results, [1] and [2], experimental tests are required to fully qualify the numerical models with static destructive testing required to validate the progressive damage model.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to express their gratitude for the helpful assistance and insight provided by the team at DERA Farnborough, through which this research is funded, in particular John House, Ian Grant, Anthony Pritchard and Sue Mercy.

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